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D5.1 - Branding and Quality Mark Design Inception Report

WP5: Governance and Business Sustainability

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Executive Summary

Quality of operations, products, services etc. are fundamental for the success of organizations. It is thus important to establish a set of evaluation criteria, a **quality mark** (QM), to monitor the outcomes and steer organization's activities. By being awarded with one or more QMs for its products and services, a Centre of Excellence (CoE) such as BioExcel can instil confidence and trust in its user community and enable it to develop a good reputation more widely. Quality should be easily associated with the visual brand of the CoE and boost its profile.

This document describes how BioExcel CoE plans to create meaningful QMs that offer a positive contribution to the overall branding exercise and underpin the existing visual brand with deeper meaning. The QM development will be done by two approaches. The *top-down approach* (section 2) starts with the overall mission and vision of the centre and analyses how they underpin quality standards for specific products, services and activities. The latter three categories are analysed in the *bottom-up approach* (section 3) for development of criteria and guidelines for each of the main outcomes of our work - software applications as a product, software as a service, support and training activities.

Development of quality standards is a major undertaking. It is not a primary activity of BioExcel and therefore we aimed to adopt or adapt existing standards to suit our particular needs. In the development process we have, or plan to, actively engage with third party organizations.

In terms of achieving sustainable operations, BioExcel is in the process of establishment and bootstrapping of a legal entity. We here introduce the preliminary stages of work that will clearly be of most benefit to the sustainable entity, but which also meet the project requirements through addressing the sustainability objective.

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1 Introduction

As a CoE, BioExcel strives for high standards across all areas. Those standards are fundamental for the achievement of excellence in *software*, *usability* and *support* - the three pillars of the centre's organizational framework:

Meeting the standards and achieving a high level of quality in BioExcel outputs will be one of our main hallmarks and in turn strengthen the brand of BioExcel. Quality will underpin the design of our business model and define our business plan, it will build trust among our collaborators and wider user community in our products and services. Our aim is that the BioExcel brand, with its recognizable name, logo, and portfolio, will be associated with the image of a strong, reliable and trustworthy organization.

The **Quality Marks** (QMs) described in this document will serve three purposes. Firstly, they will help us measure the quality of our work internally and point to areas in need of improvement. Secondly, they will present external parties with the criteria against which we measure outcomes of our work and thus enshrine our commitment to quality and reliability. Thirdly, a longer-term aim is that the QMs will be used as part of a certification program for the validation of *third-party* products and services across the Centre's excellence area.

Initially, we will focus on QMs for several of our main activities, namely the development of software, provision of services, support and training. To a large extent they encompass core activities in WP1 (Code Optimization & Scaling), WP2 (Convergence HPC/HPDA and Improved Usability), WP3 (Community, Support and Use Cases) and WP4 (Dissemination and Training), respectively.

Development of standards is a major undertaking which requires enormous efforts over many years. International organizations such as ISO have dedicated teams working constantly on the development of reference quality marks. For our needs we have adapted existing work in the area as-is or with modifications. We are also exploring long-term collaborations with organizations who are major actors in this area.

Even where a quality design methodology is not explicitly followed, e.g. the Quality by Design approach described by Juran¹, or the Total Quality Management approach², many activities can be design-led. In BioExcel we will only indirectly influence many of our products and services because they will remain under the ownership of the development teams. We, therefore, propose a more casual approach which will, nevertheless, result in quality outputs that we are able to measure. Quality will be designed into our products and services working from both the top-down and from the bottom-up. We first discuss the *top-down* elements of our approach before exploring the initial *bottom-up* features.

2 Top-Down Conceptual Design

The CoE is developing from being purely a project to building an independent legal entity, which will provide products and services to paying customers, as well as maintaining open access to the publicly funded OS tools and services. Therefore, we must start to clarify what the cultural values of the CoE are: what it wants to be, why it wants to be that and how all of that will be achieved. This activity is a process that involves conceptual work and which feeds directly into the “corporate brand” of BioExcel. Clearly, this activity relates to the sustainable entity but the work to achieve that begins here within the project, where we initiate the branding and quality mark processes, which will be beneficial to both sides of BioExcel.

2.1 The High-Level Top-Down View

At the highest level, the considerations about what an organisation is, and what it will be, are very conceptual. As such, this kind of thinking follows a number of structured thought processes. One form of a nominal thought structure is illustrated below.

¹ Juran, J.M. (1986). "The Quality Trilogy: A Universal Approach to Managing for Quality". Quality Progress

² <https://managementhelp.org/quality/total-quality-management.htm>

Figure 1 Top-down view of Quality-based Organisational Design

2.1.1 Outline

In outline, the three stages of organisational design (Branding, Planning and Operating) reflect the purpose of any organisation.

- In the **branding** stage the conceptual aspects of the organisation are developed (vision, principles, purpose) and they become the message that initiates the marketing campaign and informs the continuing presence of the brand in a market. One significant aspect of the branding stage is the development of a memorable visual branding. Such branding has to embody the conceptual payload of the design decisions made so far and to present these in an easily memorable manner. The surface layer of the visual brand is a logo. BioExcel already has a distinctive and memorable logo, which is being promoted across all promotional material including an introductory animation clip, colour scheme, flyer, poster and website designs in order to build on its acceptance in the marketplace.
- In the **planning** stage, we will explore how the principles of branding underpin the design of organisational processes, structures & their purpose and justification.

- In the final **operating** stage, we will deploy the results of our planning and apply them to executable processes and structures which will be implemented and deployed in a manner that can be used by management to understand how well the organisation is performing and whether and when they may need to make changes.

2.1.2 Detail

Below we detail the individual top-view design concepts as shown in Figure 1, which highlight the main information flow. It is important to emphasize that Organizational Design is an ongoing process, and there are also information backflows that improve and re-iterate design steps upstream; e.g. realizing operational plans and goals might mean re-visiting the organizational principles as the scope of operations gets clarified.

With the consortium members, we will consider each concept in more detail. This collective consideration will shape the scope and range of activities the organisation will engage in. In effect, the thinking that emerges in these discussions will provide an outline for the business plan that will be derived in D5.4 and updated in D5.5. These discussions are yet to be held and the content below is provided for illustrative purposes and as a potential starting point for the collective discussions.

Vision

Purpose: Define what the BioExcel CoE wants to be?

Candidate concepts:

- To be the sole source of software, services and expert knowledge at the heart of the Computational Biomolecular Research community.

Principles

Purpose: What kind of organisation does the BioExcel CoE want to be?

Candidate concepts:

- Trusted service and software supplier in the community.
- Trusted and collaborative community member.
- Source of trusted knowledge.
- Outcome focussed.
- Innovative and agile community member.

Purpose

Purpose: What is the BioExcel CoE for?

Candidate concepts:

- To deliver value to our clients by providing high quality software, services and expert knowledge.
- To deliver value to our clients by providing high quality training and support systems that are appropriate to their needs.

Mission

Purpose: What does the BioExcel CoE want to achieve?

Candidate concepts:

- To make a positive difference to the Biomolecular Research community through developing and delivering the industry-leading examples of quality software, services, expert knowledge, training and support systems.

Positioning

Purpose: How will the BioExcel CoE work with its clients, suppliers, competitors and other related entities.

Candidate concepts:

- The BioExcel CoE will be a trusted supplier in the Biomolecular Research domain.
- The BioExcel CoE will lead opinion in the Biomolecular Research domain.
- The BioExcel CoE will support the discovery and delivery of excellent results in the Biomolecular Research domain.

Critical Success Factors

Purpose: What the BioExcel CoE must attain/obtain to achieve the required positioning

Candidate concepts:

- A positive impact on addressing clients' needs.
 - Agility to respond to changing needs.
 - Thought leadership in key areas.
- Skilled, innovative, committed and motivated staff.
- Productive external networks.
- Resilient and efficient business performance.
- An excellent reputation.

It is worth noting that this stage of top-down thinking is the first point of intersection with the bottom-up design that follows in the next section. Many of the Critical Success Factors we will adopt are built into the standards we will work to. In achieving these standards, BioExcel tangibly demonstrates its credentials within its market in order that:

- *Its existing customers and users are able to build trust in its products and services.*
- *An excellent reputation is developed within the remaining marketplace.*

Plans and Goals

Purpose: How is BioExcel CoE going to achieve the required positioning

Candidate concepts:

- Delivering on its priorities
- Increasing and exploiting its Innovation potential
- Working as a trusted partner
 - Crucial stakeholder management
- Striving for excellence in results
- Investing in its sustainable future

Processes and Structures

Purpose: The activities in which the BioExcel CoE needs to participate, in order to succeed in its achieving and maintaining its leading position in the Biomolecular Research community.

Candidate concepts:

- Risk management
- Innovation management
- Quality control
- Customer relationship management
- Supplier relationship management
- Customer needs awareness
- Market monitoring

Purpose: The management and delivery structures that must be developed to succeed

Candidate concepts:

- Agile management team
- Flat, responsive management hierarchy
- Effective operational focus
- Rational team organisation

Actions and KPIs

Purpose (Actions): What will the BioExcel CoE actually do in terms of its day to day operations

Candidate concepts:

- Listen to clients
- Monitor the market
- Deliver packaged software
- Deliver meaningful services
- Offer expert consultancy
- Provided effective client support
- Internal development
 - Organisation
 - Personnel

Purpose (Success KPIs): How will the BioExcel CoE know it has finished an operation?

Candidate concepts:

- Quantitative KPIs
 - Business process focus
- Normative and stretch metrics

Purpose (Monitoring KPIs): How will the BioExcel CoE know how well it has performed an operation

Candidate concepts:

- Qualitative KPIs
 - Client-side focus
- Normative and stretch metrics

3 Bottom Up Design Elements

As stated in Section 2, there are top-down and bottom-up approaches to design that intersect in the area of establishing quality. In this section we explore the issues of how BioExcel will determine which standards it will adopt in order to demonstrate the quality of its products and services to our users.

Any standard enforcing sufficiently high quality will award a “Quality Mark” to those entities that succeed in meeting the set evaluation criteria. A quality mark is a symbol which indicates that a product, or service meets a recognized standard of quality. The degree of quality will normally be governed by a regulatory body operating in the domain of concern. Such regulatory bodies can be national or international.

There are two aspects of quality that are important to distinguish when evaluating a quality mark candidate. Firstly the “business process” aspects of the underlying activity covers areas such as sustainability, community engagement, support channels, availability and licensing. Secondly is the question if the tool or service meets its technical and scientific requirements. For example, a software package might have full marks in terms of its project governance, and perform high-quality analytics, yet execute slowly due to a sub-optimal implementation. Similarly, a service might in some cases produce results that are no longer considered scientifically valid, even if the service has high availability and excellent support track record.

Therefore, we acknowledge that such aspects of overall quality are also of considerable interest and importance for the scientific community. For this reason, we propose to build on the example set by the HADDOCK community, where blind challenges (e.g. D3R and CAPRI) are regularly run in order to establish exactly these kinds technical quality values.

We now discuss the approach we have taken in the BioExcel Quality Mark design and the progress we have made to date.

3.1 Introduction to Areas Suitable for Quality Mark Allocation

The most important element in the initial stages of the bottom up approach is the establishment of our quality standards in order to build trust and reputation. To be of value in terms of establishing and reinforcing the credibility of the BioExcel products and services, the custodianship of these quality marks must be independent of BioExcel, as well as externally and objectively evaluated.

The issues around quality that we begin to scope out below are based on the existing approach to standardisation carried out through international initiatives. That approach decouples the general way that products or services are “manufactured”, managed and delivered, from the ability of an individual product or service to meet user-specific (functional, non-functional, technical and scientific) requirements. The former is of interest in the quality / standardisation context, where an organisational, systems-level, view is of primary importance. Therefore, the *specific* design aspects associated with the ability of a *particular* product or service to meet *individual* user needs are

addressed through the technical specification of that product or service and this activity falls outside the scope of this initiation of the BioExcel Quality Marks. We will, however, address such issues in the subsequent work we design and deliver.

In terms of reinforcing the credibility of BioExcel products and services, we introduce here the four areas where the application of standards will help to establish the quality of the BioExcel brand (each area is explored in detail in the sections that follow):

- Software Applications
 - We define a software application as a package of software programs, code libraries, data structures, etc. that a potential user downloads and installs on a machine they manage. They have full control over all aspects of running the software.
 - In BioExcel, software can include stand-alone applications, bundles of applications in the form of workflow building blocks, as well as multiple complete workflows.
 - For the purposes of expressing the excellence of the work we carry out, we assert that it is the quality of the written code development processes and rules that govern the general suitability of the code to support meaningful business and operational interactions. For this reason, we will measure software quality in relation to how well it meets its function and objectives. This will be measured using parameters from ISO/IEC 12207 and ISO/IEC/IEEE 15288 as embodied in the Software Sustainability Institute guides (see section 3.2.1).
- Software Services
 - We define that a software service is composed of *software packages* installed and running *remotely* under control by the user, including the *communication* mechanisms required to access it; as well as the (implied or explicit) *contractual agreement* made between the user and the provider.
 - BioExcel stand-alone applications and workflow bundles can also be exposed as services, we will consider these opportunities during the business modelling phase.
 - For the purposes of expressing the excellence of the work we carry out, we assert that it is the Quality of Service (QoS) a user experiences when using the service that governs its suitability. For this reason, we will measure service quality in relation to how well it satisfies the QoS parameters we agree with our clients. This will be measured using parameters from ISO/IEC 20000, ITIL v4 and FitSM as guides. (See section 3.3)
- Support Services
 - We define that a support service is delivered by people, remotely or locally. A local support service is delivered by an expert working on site at a customer location, usually through the execution of a consultancy contract. A remote support service is delivered off site by an expert at their own location (or roaming), usually through the execution of a help-desk and/or technical support contract.

- For the purposes of expressing the excellence of the work we carry out, we assert that it is the user experience when using the support service that determines its suitability. However, we note that there are very few standardization activities carried out in this area. (See Section 3.4)
- Training Services
 - We define that training services are conducted in two modes: Face-to-face (e.g. training courses and seminars) and remotely (e.g. pre-recorded video tutorials or streaming of live training sessions).
 - For the purposes of expressing the excellence of the work we carry out, we assert that (regardless of the training delivery mode being face to face or remote) it is the user experience when using the training service that determines its suitability. Many standards exist in the education and teaching, but few that focus on training, even ISO activity in the area of e-learning was withdrawn³. However, we will explore the Training and Learning Standards (2012) as a source of suitable standards we can adopt. A partner in BioExcel, AcrossLimits, recently became an accredited training provider⁴. We will therefore also use the guidelines developed by AcrossLimits during the accreditation process as a baseline. (See Section 3.5)

3.2 Software Applications

Software development is a main activity of BioExcel and our core applications are crucial for the scientific work of thousands of researchers world-wide. Thus, it is critically important, in particular for impact within the user communities, that we set and adhere to high quality standards in terms of: application usability, maintainability and sustainability, as well as performance, scalability and efficiency in the light of extreme-computing.

The need and importance of high-quality software has been recognized and more attention given to the topic in recent years. Many journals (e.g. Journal of Open Source Software, [JOSS](#)) have checklists for evaluation of software as a required part of its peer-review process⁵. Journal of Open Research Software ([JORS](#))⁶ promotes “software with high reuse potential”, which is “professionally archived, preserved, and is openly available”. BioExcel already took a big step in that direction by publishing a white paper⁷ on best practices for software development. Our KPIs, which are related to software development in WP1, reflect to a large extent the push towards excellence in software development.

³ ISO/IEC 19796-1:2005 at <https://www.iso.org/news/2006/02/Ref992.html>

⁴ AcrossLimits Ltd. is licensed by The National Commission for Further and Higher Education as a Further and Higher Education Institution

⁵ https://joss.readthedocs.io/en/latest/review_checklist.html

⁶ <https://openresearchsoftware.metajnl.com>

⁷ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1194634>

3.2.1 Evaluation criteria

We base our evaluation criteria on the excellent work done by the Software Sustainability Institute⁸ (SSI, www.software.ac.uk) and specifically as described by Jackson et al⁹. The report represents a checklist of assessments covering a full spectrum of characteristics based on the ISO/IEC 9126-1 “Software engineering —Product quality” standard¹⁰. The standard is currently under review for updates¹¹.

High-quality software would satisfy a large number of the criteria in the standard, which are listed In Annex I. Evaluation of software applications includes answering each of the criteria questions with “yes”, “no” or “n/a”. In cases where the question does not offer a boolean or numeric answer, we accept “yes” for the cases where the (arguably subjective) evaluation is largely positive. Finally, a score for each category is given by the ratio of positive and total applicable answers, i.e.

$$\text{Score} = \text{count}(\text{“yes”}) / (\text{count}(\text{“yes”}) + \text{count}(\text{“no”}))$$

Thus, fulfilling all criteria (100%) will produce a score of 1. For visualization of the results we use a radar chart for representation and analysis. Same procedure is applied to evaluations in the other categories – services, support and training.

We are currently in discussions with SSI regarding future development of the quality mark. Our plans include the establishment of a formal collaboration agreement and potentially a joint certification process.

⁸ <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/MCSE.2013.133>

⁹ <https://www.software.ac.uk/sites/default/files/SSI-SoftwareEvaluationCriteria.pdf>

¹⁰ <http://www.sqa.net/iso9126.html>

¹¹ <https://www.iso.org/standard/35733.html>

3.2.2 Assessment of BioExcel applications and tools

Using the evaluation criteria in Annex I and procedure described above, we evaluated GROMACS and HADDOCK, two of the core applications developed by BioExcel, and assessed their current quality level. Results are shown in the following Figure 1 and Figure 2:

Figure 1. GROMACS Quality Mark assessment

Figure 2. HADDOCK Quality Mark assessment

3.3 Software as a Service

Computer software is usually packaged as a standalone application (or in a code library) and delivered along with documentation and/or media to the users who install and run it on their own hardware. Computer services, on the other hand, are a delivery model where the software runs in one location (usually under maintenance and control by the code developers) and is operated from another location by the end-users.

This abstract experience is no longer directly related to the specification of instructions or of the suitability of byte-streams, it is more directly related to the experience of finding and using the service. Here, the Quality of Service (QoS), which considers issues of discoverability, accessibility, availability, reliability and dependability is more important.

For the purposes of building trust and building a good reputation, we intend to comply with a well-known published standard. We have carried out a preliminary review of common IT service standards and, based on their criteria profiles, we have analysed several approaches to service standardisation and devised three dismissal categories leading to a final selection category. In the analyses below, we do not consider financial costs; however, it should be noted that the selected approach is open source.

- Rejected Category 1: Not yet Relevant
 - **DevOps**¹² is too close to software development to be truly an IT Service Management tool but it might be useful later as a means of managing how BioExcel software evolves into a service.
 - **COBIT**¹³ Focusses on IT service governance rather than ITSM but it might be useful later on when we are developing processes and defining roles within the sustainable entity.
- Rejected Category 2: Incorrect Scope
 - **Tivoli**¹⁴ is an IBM ITSM tool that is tightly bound into IBM internal processes and is, therefore, too specialised to meet our needs
 - **eTOM**¹⁵ is an ITSM too that focusses only on business processes. It offers only partial coverage and is unfit for this reason.
- Rejected Category 3: Overly complex
 - **ITIL v4**¹⁶ is a comprehensive ITSM and is used widely in the IT Service sector. However, achieving ITIL certification is a complex undertaking and requires a great deal of time and effort. ITIL is clearly designed for large corporate structures and this is something that BioExcel is unlikely to ever have.
 - **ISO/IEC 2000**¹⁷ is a set of ITSM standards that align well with the ITIL philosophy. For reasons associated with its similarity to ITIL, certification commits to a complex and time-consuming process; it is also aligned most closely with ITIL v2 and is becoming outdated. For these reasons we reject this approach.
- Selected Category and Proposed Approach
 - **FitSM**¹⁸ offers a lightweight approach to deploying ITSM. It adopts parts of ITIL and ISO/IEC 2000 but packages them in a manner that is applicable to small organisations. Despite the approach being derived out of an FP7 project (FedSM¹⁹) and, therefore, designed with projects in mind, it is gaining traction in the commercial sector amongst smaller enterprises and has gained TÜV²⁰ approval. An additional benefit is that all resources are available freely under a Creative Commons license.

Moreover, for the purpose of demonstrating the excellence of the work we carry out, we assert that it is the QoS a user experiences when *accessing* the service that governs its suitability, and, therefore, its quality. For this reason, we will

¹² <https://developer.ibm.com/articles/d-devops-drive-quality-assurance-testing/>

¹³ <http://www.isaca.org/cobit/pages/faqs.aspx>

¹⁴ [https://www-](https://www-01.ibm.com/software/support/lifecycleapp/PLCDetail.wss?synkey=T380276I14240V97&from=spf)

[01.ibm.com/software/support/lifecycleapp/PLCDetail.wss?synkey=T380276I14240V97&from=spf](https://www-01.ibm.com/software/support/lifecycleapp/PLCDetail.wss?synkey=T380276I14240V97&from=spf)

¹⁵ <https://www.tmforum.org/business-process-framework/>

¹⁶

https://www.itiltraining.com/uk/about?gclid=EAIaIQobChMIgr6glJCK4wIVRYfVCh3A_gPZEAAYAAAEgKDFvD_BwE

¹⁷ <https://www.iso.org/standard/51986.html>

¹⁸ <https://fitsm.itemo.org/>

¹⁹ <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/104760/factsheet/en>

²⁰ Technischer Überwachungsverein, the German technical standardisation authority

measure service quality in relation to how well it satisfies the QoS parameters we agree with our clients in the contracts we will conclude with users.

An initial catalogue of potential services is being compiled and will be available in D5.2.

From these we have selected as a sample, the MDWeb BioExcel service and have run a preliminary survey²¹ to determine a benchmark for the BioExcel service maturity modelling and development exercise. The initial findings are presented in Figure 3 below and the criteria that were explored to achieve these findings are presented in Annex II.

Figure 3. MDWeb Quality Mark Assessment

From this figure we can immediately see in which areas additional work is required to maintain a high-quality service offering, for instance Configuration Management has not yet seen a high priority, making it more time-consuming to re-deploy the service (e.g. for scalability or availability), while the service has managed Continual Service Improvement well (e.g. keeping the service aligned with user expectations). Electing which areas are most important to prioritize is

²¹ This was a technical quality survey and was conducted with the service owner

a complex task that depend on the service details and potential/existing user base.

3.4 Support

We define a *support service* as: an expert service delivered by a person or persons, remotely or locally. For the purposes of expressing the excellence of the work we carry out in this context, we assert that it is the user experience when consuming the support service that determines its suitability. However, we note that there are few standardization activities carried out in this area. A brief discussion of our limited options is presented below.

A **local support service** is delivered by an expert working on site at a customer location, usually through the execution of a consultancy contract. While there is some activity in the area of generic consultancy quality standards, through the Matrix approach²², this is still very much a nascent activity and even its own information pack describes it as “a boutique” approach. In the main, the QMs of consultancy support services are domain-based e.g. ISO 9001 (Quality) and GDPR IMS (Data Privacy) standards. Therefore, the BioExcel consultancy QMs will be based on relevant service domain standards and work will be carried out in relation to the type of consultancy support services that BioExcel is likely to provide, as there are costs associated with qualifying in each domain and we need to be sure that our cost recovery requirements aren’t too onerous.

A **remote support service** is delivered off site by an expert at their home location (or roaming), usually through the execution of a help-desk and/or technical support contract. Standards for help desk support services are an emerging area. We considered Help Desk Institute (HDI)²³ and Service Desk Institute (SDI)²⁴ Certification but they are both highly US-centric and is also still in the embryonic stages of development. For this reason, we favour a more pragmatic approach: the EGI help desk function²⁵ which has emerged as a de facto standard in the e-infrastructure community.

From the limited exposure we have had with industrial researchers, we absolutely understand that an “enterprise level” service is required by them and we define this as mainly associated with, for example, the availability, dependability, utility and resilience of the service. Such parameters are usually defined in an SLA and are assigned values where, for instance, availability and dependability would e.g. guarantee the service is accessible within 2 minutes regardless of the time of day or day of year. Another parameter is resolution period, where the solution to any problem is guaranteed to be delivered within e.g. 2 days. It is often the case that this type of service quality discrimination is aggregated into standardised service classes where most clients will be happy to choose from a menu such as: Gold, Silver, and Bronze, service classes, leaving only specialized users to negotiate bespoke SLAs.

²² <https://www.clearquality.co.uk/matrix-standard>

²³ <https://www.thinkhdi.com/>

²⁴ <https://www.servicedeskintstitute.com/>

²⁵ <https://www.egi.eu/internal-services/helpdesk/>

The lack of compelling standards in this area means we have to be creative. Therefore, as part of the process of assigning a QM to BioExcel Support services we will develop a list of support service offerings to add to the service catalogue along with its “readiness level” which will be based on criteria we will design through consultation with interested parties through industry fora.

3.5 Training

One of BioExcel’s main objectives is to reduce the skill gap between traditional scientific computing practices (desktop or small cluster usage) and the requirements for efficient usage of extreme-scale compute resources - exascale machines, accelerators, hybrid systems etc. We have already pioneered a training program which incorporates training needs analysis, development of competency profiles and mapping of required skill sets to existing training offerings, as well as expanding on the latter as needed.

A successful and quality program needs to ensure relevance of the offered training; adequate skillset of trainees enrolled in the program; high expertise of the trainers; smooth event organization and logistics; post-mortem analysis of outcomes; planning of follow-up activities; building long-term relationship with trainees etc. Such aspects thus need to be considered when developing a quality mark for training. In BioExcel the offerings take shape into several different categories such as 3-5-day long courses, 1-2-day workshops, webinars and virtual training.

Unlike the case of services, there don’t seem to exist well defined and accepted international standard for activities in the specific context of our training offerings which are described above. [ISO.org](https://www.iso.org/) lists several related standards but most of them don’t address our needs²⁶, or have been withdrawn^{27,28}. Some may be applicable^{29,30} and they will be considered, but nevertheless the lack of a widely adopted international standard shows how difficult it is to generalize.

Despite the lack of such a standard though, international initiatives are continuously putting efforts in the area: IntraHealth International has been working for many years on guidance documents³¹ and tools³² for ensuring quality of training; LifeTrain implements a list³³ of nine quality standards for evaluation of courses. The list is used extensively across the IMI Education and

²⁶ <https://www.iso.org/standard/50960.html>

²⁷ <https://www.iso.org/standard/53392.html>

²⁸ <https://www.iso.org/standard/33934.html>

²⁹ <https://www.iso.org/news/2006/02/Ref992.html>

³⁰ <https://www.iso.org/standard/62825.html>

³¹ https://www.intrahealth.org/sites/ihweb/files/media/training-and-learning-standards/Training_Learning_Standards_2012_English.pdf

³² <https://www.intrahealth.org/sites/ihweb/files/attachment-files/Programming%2520for%2520Training%2520.pdf>

³³ <http://www.lifetrain.eu/about/quality/>

Training network; CodeRefinery, a training network for research software development in the Nordics, develops guidelines designing lessons³⁴; etc.

In addition, BioExcel partners have an active role in ongoing work in the area. We are part of the ISCB (www.iscb.org) education committee, looking at certification of courses. We are also represented in the Carpentries (www.carpentries.org) Council. We have joint activities with ELIXIR on quality and with RITrain on impact. Finally, AcrossLimits is a certified training centre accredited by the EC to deliver training courses funded centrally through EU funds. As such, BioExcel is well placed to contribute into the standardisation arena in relation to the creation of a nascent training standard that is both widely applicable at the higher levels yet easily configurable at the lower levels.

Building on existing efforts, our initial work will focus on the development of a *Course Quality Mark*. It will focus on events where BioExcel is the prime organizer and we are in full control of their planning and execution. As a starting point, an initial list has been drafted in Annex III.

Courses are often composed of several modules, which are also commonly delivered standalone during e.g. 1-2-day workshops. Thus, building on the course QM, we anticipate extending the guidelines to cover recommendations on the module content and delivery methods.

Finally, the course and workshop guidelines will be amended and adapted to cover the ongoing webinars and upcoming virtual training activities.

4 Future Development Process

In the current inception report we have presented initial list of criteria for four different quality marks. Those will be applied to all of our relevant products and services. We will also engage with third-parties (in particular CoEs, related initiatives, collaboration partners etc.) and promote our QMs as a valuable tool for their own development processes.

Based on our experience in their application, as well as feedback from the third-parties, the QMs will be continuously revised and refined for relevance and accuracy. Even though we don't expect BioExcel to be recognized as an authority in certification of standards, our aim is to initially raise awareness and pave the road towards wider adoption of QM metrics as means to achieving high standards of product and service provisioning in the whole ecosystem.

In order to facilitate the wider adoption, we will develop a user-friendly web application for simple and quick quality measurements. We have developed spreadsheet models for some of the QMs already. Once the models cover all of the BioExcel QMs, they will be agreed with the consortium before we convert them into online tools. The tools will allow external users to quickly assess their

³⁴ <https://github.com/coderefinery/manuals/blob/master/lesson-design.md>

own products/services by filling out the relevant questionnaire. The online tool will then present a radar chart with a quick overview of the extent to which the QM has been covered, similar to the figures in section 3 above.

5 Future Certification Process

The certification of external quality standards depends upon an independent objective assessment of organisational policies, internal processes and management rules. Before the assessment takes place a significant investment in effort is required to ensure that all required elements of the relevant standard are fully implemented and deployed, with audited evidence provided to demonstrate that they are being properly managed. There are also some considerable financial commitments to be made in the use of some standards³⁵, so we anticipate that while progress will be made in implementing and deploying some elements of such standards, it is unlikely that we will be able to achieve certification during the life of the project as other sources of income or investment will be required in order to fund these activities.

Once achieved, we will actively promote the fact that BioExcel has achieved (another) QM accreditation. Promotion will take place vertically within the community we service directly and also horizontally into the CoE community we are part of and into the EC to demonstrate our continuing commitment to maintaining a sustainable CoE.

Annex I - Software Evaluation Criteria Checklist³⁶

USABILITY

Understandability

- How straightforward is it to understand:
 - What the software does and its purpose?
 - The intended market and users of the software?
 - The software's basic functions?
 - The software's advanced functions?
- High-level description of what/who the software is for is available.
- High-level description of what the software does is available.
- High-level description of how the software works is available.
- Design rationale is available – why it does it the way it does.
- Architectural overview, with diagrams, is available.
- Descriptions of intended use cases are available.
- Case studies of use are available.

Documentation

³⁵ ISO 20000, ISO 27000, etc.

³⁶ List is taken from <https://www.software.ac.uk/sites/default/files/SSI-SoftwareEvaluationCriteria.pdf>

- Looking at the user documentation, what is its
 - Quality?
 - Completeness?
 - Accuracy?
 - Appropriateness?
 - Clarity?
- Provides a high-level overview of the software.
- Partitioned into sections for users, user-developers and developers (depending on the software).
- States assumed background and expertise of the reader, for each class of user.
- Lists resources for further information.
- Further information is suitable for the level of the reader, for each class of user.
- Is task-oriented.
- Consists of clear, step-by-step instructions.
- Gives examples of what the user can see at each step e.g. screenshots or command-line excerpts.
- For problems and error messages, the symptoms and step-by-step solutions are provided.
- Does not use terms like “intuitive”, “user friendly”, “easy to use”, “simple” or “obviously”, unless as part of quotes from satisfied users
- States command names and syntax, says what menus to use, lists parameters and error messages exactly as they appear or should be typed.
- Uses `teletype-style` fonts for command-line inputs and outputs, source code fragments, function names, class names etc.
- For Java, the package names of classes are stated the first time a class is mentioned.
- English language descriptions of commands or errors are provided but only to complement the above.
- Plain-text files (e.g. READMEs) use indentation and underlining (e.g. `===` and `---`) to structure the text.
- Plain-text files (e.g. READMEs) do not use TAB characters to indent the text.
- API documentation e.g. Javadoc or Doxygen, documents APIs completely e.g. configuration files, property names etc.
- Is held under version control alongside the code.
- Is on the project web site.
- Documentation on the project web site makes it clear what version of the software the documentation applies to.

Buildability

- How straightforward is it to:
 - Meet the prerequisites for building the software on a build platform?
 - Build the software on a build platform?
- Web site has instructions for building the software
- Source distributions have instructions for building the software.

- An automated build (e.g. Make, ANT, custom solution) is used to build the software.
- Web site lists all third-party dependencies that are not bundled, along with web addresses, suitable versions, licences and whether these are mandatory or optional.
- Source distributions list all third-party dependencies that are not bundled, along with web addresses, suitable versions, licences and whether these are mandatory or optional.
- Dependency management is used to automatically download dependencies (e.g. ANT, Ivy, Maven or custom solution).
- All mandatory third-party dependencies are currently available.
- All optional third-party dependencies are currently available.
- Tests are provided to verify the build has succeeded.

Installability

- How straightforward is it to:
 - Meet the prerequisites for the software on a target platform?
 - Install the software onto a target platform?
 - Configure the software following installation for use?
 - Verify the installation for use?
- Note that in some cases build and install may be one and the same.
- Web site has instructions for installing the software.
- Binary distributions have instructions for installing the software.
- Web site lists all third-party dependencies that are not bundled, along with web addresses, suitable versions, licences and whether these are mandatory or optional.
- Binary distributions list all third-party dependencies that are not bundled, along with web addresses, suitable versions, licences and whether these are mandatory or optional.
- Dependency management is used to automatically download dependencies (e.g. ANT, Ivy, Maven or custom solution).
- All mandatory third-party dependencies are currently available.
- All optional third-party dependencies are currently available.
- Tests are provided to verify the install has succeeded.
- When an archive (e.g. TAR.GZ or ZIP) is unpacked, it creates a single directory with the files within. It does not spread its contents all over the current directory.
- When software is installed, its contents are organised into sub-directories (e.g. docs for documentation, libs for dependent libraries) as appropriate.
- All source and binary distributions contain a README.TXT with project name, web site, how/where to get help, version, date, licence and copyright (or where to find this information), location of entry point into user doc.
- All GUIs contain a Help menu with commands to see the project name, web site, how/where to get help, version, date, licence and copyright (or where to find this information), location of entry point into user doc.
- All other content distributed as an archive contains a README.TXT with project name, web site, nature, how /where to get help, date.

- Installers allow user to select where to install software.
- Uninstallers uninstall every file or warns user of any files that were not removed and where these are.

Learnability

- How straightforward is it to learn how to achieve:
 - Basic functional tasks?
 - Advanced functional tasks?
- A getting started guide is provided outlining a basic example of using the software.
- Instructions are provided for many basic use cases.
- Instructions are provided supporting all use cases.
- Reference guides are provided for all command- line, GUI and configuration options.
- API documentation is provided for user- developers and developers.

SUSTAINABILITY AND MAINTAINABILITY

Identity

- To what extent is the identity of the project/software clear and unique both within its application domain and generally?
- Project/software has its own domain name.
- Project/software has a logo.
- Project/software has a distinct name within its application area. A search by Google on the name plus keywords from the application area throws up the project web site in the first page of matches.
- Project/software has a distinct name regardless of its application area. A search by Google on the name plus keywords from the application area throws up the project web site in the first page of matches.
- Project/software name does not throw up embarrassing “Did you mean...” hits on Google.
- Project/software name does not violate an existing trade-mark.
- Project/software name is trade-marked.

Copyright

- To what extent is it clear who wrote the software and owns its copyright?
- Website states copyright.
- Web site states who developed/develops the software, funders etc.
- If there are multiple websites then these all state exactly the same copyright, licencing and authorship.
- Each source code file has a copyright statement.
- If supported by the language, each source code file has a copyright statement embedded within a constant.
- Each source code file has a licence header.

Licencing

- Has an appropriate licence been adopted?
- Website states licence.

- Software (source and binaries) has a licence.
- Software has an open source licence.
- Software has an Open Software Initiative (OSI)- recognised licence (<http://www.opensource.org/>).

Governance

- To what extent does the project make its management, or how its software development is managed, transparent?
- Project has defined a governance policy.
- Governance policy is publicly available.

Community

- To what extent does/will an active user community exist for this product?
- Web site has statement of number of users/developers/members.
- Web site has success stories.
- Web site has quotes from satisfied users.
- Web site has a list of important partners or collaborators.
- Web site has a list of the project's publications.
- Web site has a list of third-party publications that cite the software.
- Web site has a list of software that uses/bundles this software.
- Users are requested to cite the project if publishing papers based on results derived from the software.
- Users are required to cite a boilerplate citation if publishing papers based on results derived from the software.
- Users exist who are not members of the project.
- Developers exist who are not members of the project.

Accessibility

- To what extent is the software accessible?
- Binary distributions are available (whether for free, payment, registration).
- Binary distributions are freely available.
- Binary distributions are available without the need for any registration or authorisation of access by the project.
- Source distributions are available (whether for free, payment, registration).
- Source distributions are freely available.
- Source distributions are available without the need for any registration or authorisation of access by the project.
- Access to source code repository is available (whether for free, payment, registration).
- Anonymous read-only access to source code repository.
- Ability to browse source code repository online.
- Repository is hosted externally to a single organisation/institution in a sustainable third- party repository (e.g. SourceForge, GoogleCode, LaunchPad, GitHub) which will live beyond the lifetime of any current funding line.
- Downloads page shows evidence of regular releases (e.g. six monthly, bi-weekly, etc.).

Testability

- How straightforward is it to test the software to verify modifications?
- Project has unit tests.
- Project has integration tests.
- For GUIs, project uses automated GUI test frameworks.
- Project has scripts for testing scenarios that have not been automated (e.g. for testing GUIs).
- Project recommends tools to check conformance to coding standards.
- Project has automated tests to check conformance to coding standards.
- Project recommends tools to check test coverage.
- Project has automated tests to check test coverage.
- A minimum test coverage level that must be met has been defined.
- There is an automated test for this minimum test coverage level.
- Tests are automatically run nightly.
- Continuous integration is supported – tests are automatically run whenever the source code changes.
- Test results are visible to all developers/members.
- Test results are visible publicly.
- Test results are e-mailed to a mailing list.
- This e-mailing list can be subscribed to by anyone.
- Project specifies how to set up external resources e.g. FTP servers, databases for tests.
- Tests create their own files, database tables etc.

Portability

- To what extent can the software be used on other platforms?
- Application can be built on and run under Windows.
- Application can be built on and run under Windows 7.
- Application can be built on and run under Windows XP.
- Application can be built on and run under Windows Vista.
- Application can be built on and run under UNIX/Linux.
- Application can be built on and run under Solaris.
- Application can be built on and run under RedHat.
- Application can be built on and run under Debian.
- Application can be built on and run under Fedora.
- Application can be built on and run under Ubuntu.
- Application can be built on and run under MacOSX.
- Browser applications run under Internet Explorer.
- Browser applications run under Mozilla Firefox.
- Browser applications run under Google Chrome.
- Browser applications run under Opera.
- Browser applications run under Safari.

Supportability

- To what extent will the product be supported currently and in the future?
- Web site has a page describing how to get support.
- User doc has a page describing how to get support.

- Software describes how to get support (in a README for command-line tools or a Help=>About window in a GUI).
- Above pages/windows/files describe, or link to, a description of “how to ask for help” e.g. cite version number, send transcript, error logs etc.
- Project has an e-mail address.
- Project e-mail address has project domain name.
- E-mails are read by more than one person.
- E-mails are archived.
- E-mail archives are publicly readable.
- E-mail archives are searchable.
- Project has a ticketing system.
- Ticketing system is publicly readable.
- Ticketing system is searchable.
- Website has sitemap or index.
- Web site has a search facility.
- Project resources are hosted externally to a single organisation/institution in a sustainable third-party repository (e.g. SourceForge, GoogleCode, LaunchPad, GitHub) which will live beyond the lifetime of the current project.
- E-mail archives or ticketing system shows that queries are responded to within a week (not necessarily fixed, but at least looked at and a decision taken as to their priority).
- If there is a blog, it is regularly used.
- E-mail lists or forums, if present, have regular posts.

Analysability

- How straightforward is it to analyse the software’s source release to:
 - To understand its implementation architecture?
 - To understand individual source code files and how they fit into the implementation architecture?
- Source code is structured into modules or packages.
- Source code structure relates clearly to the architecture or design.
- Project files for IDEs are provided.
- Source system code repository is a revision control
- Structure of the source code repository and how it maps to the software’s components is documented.
- Source releases are snapshots of the repository.
- Source code is commented.
- Source code comments are written in an API document generation mark-up language e.g. JavaDoc or Doxygen.
- Source code is laid out and indented well.
- Source code uses sensible class, package and variable names.
- There are no old source code files that should be handled by version control e.g. “SomeComponentOld.java”.
- There is no commented out code.
- There are no TODOs in the code.
- Auto-generated source code is in separate directories from other source code.
- How to regenerate the auto-generated source code is documented.

- Coding standards are recommended by the project.
- Coding standards are required to be observed.
- Project-specific coding standards are consistent with community or generic coding standards (e.g. for C, Java, FORTRAN etc.).

Changeability

- How straightforward is it to modify the software to:
 - Address issues?
 - Modify functionality?
 - Add new functionality?
- Project has defined a policy for contributions.
- Contributions policy is publicly available.
- Contributors retain copyright/IP of their contributions.
 - This issue is complicated by the fact that
 - Many originators do not understand their rights.
 - IP laws are not consistent across the EU nations.
 - Individual institutions have their own rules that apply to the results of work conducted there.
 - For BioExcel, we need to find a way of understanding how ownership can be managed consistently and uniformly.
- Users, user-developers and developers who are not project members can contribute.
- Project has defined a stability/deprecation policy for components, APIs etc.
- Stability/deprecation policy is publicly available.
- Releases document deprecated components/APIs in that release.
- Releases document removed/changed components/APIs in that release.
- Changes in the source code repository are e-mailed to a mailing list.
- This e-mailing list can be subscribed to by anyone.

Evolvability

- To what extent will the product be developed in the future:
 - For a future release?
 - Within a roadmap for the product?
- Web site describes project roadmap or plans or milestones (either on a web page or within a ticketing system).
- Web site describes how project is funded/sustained.
- Web site describes end dates of current funding lines.

Interoperability

- To what extent does the software's interoperability:
 - Meet appropriate open standards?
 - Function with required third-party components?
 - Function with optional third-party components?
- Uses open standards.
- Uses mature, ratified, non-draft open standards.
- Provides tests demonstrating compliance to open standards.

Annex II - IT Services Benchmarking Checklist

Questions Relating to Simplified FitSM Evaluation Criteria taken from the documentation available at the FitSM website³⁷

Service Management

- Do you have a Service Management Scope Statement?
- Do you have a Service Management Policy?
- Do you have a Service Management Plan?
- Do you have a Service Management System?
- Do you monitor Service Management System Effectiveness?
- Do you save the Service Management System performance results?
- Do you carry out Assessment and audits of the Service Management System results?
- Do you maintain a Service Portfolio?
 - (delivery pipeline, live service catalogue, retired service catalogue)

- Do you have a Service Portfolio Process Definition?
- Do you maintain a Service Catalogue?
- Do you have a Service Level Management Process Definition?

Service Contract Management

- Do you offer Service Level Agreements (SLAs) to your users?
- Do you conduct SLA reviews?
- Do you save the SLA review results?
- Do you compare Service Performance Results with the performance agreed in SLAs?
- Do you offer Operational Level Agreements (OLAs)?
- Are the OLAs based on Underpinning Agreements (UAs)?
- Do you conduct Agreement Reviews of the SLAs, OLAs, UAs?
- Do you monitor the Agreement performance data of service performance for SLAs?
- Do you monitor the component performance for OLAs and UAs?
- Do you have a Service Reporting Process Definition?
- Do you create Service report specifications?
- Do you have a create Service reports?
- Do you have a Service Availability Definition?
- Do you have a Continuity Process Definition?
- Do you have a Service Availability Plan?
- Do you have a Service Continuity Plan?
- Do you monitor Service Availability?
- Do you save the Service Availability monitoring results?

³⁷ <https://fitsm.itemo.org/>

Capacity Management

- Do you have a Capacity Management Process Definition?
- Do you create Capacity plans?
- Are the Capacity plans based on Performance and utilisation requirements?
- Do you monitor Service Performance and utilisation?
- Do you save the Performance and utilisation monitoring results?

Information Security Management

- Do you have an Information Security Management Process Definition?
- Do you maintain Information Security Policies?
- Have you defined Information Security Control specifications?
- Do you have an Information Security policy?
- Do you review the results of Information Security control measures?

Customer Relationship Management

- Do you have a Customer Relationship Process Definition?
- Do you maintain a Customer and contact list?
- Do you store Service review results?
- Do you store Complaint handling results?
- Do you store Customer satisfaction monitoring results?

Supplier Relationship Management

- Do you have a Supplier Relationship Process Definition?
- Do you maintain a Supplier and contact list?
- Do you store Supplier performance monitoring results?

User Incident Management

- Do you have an Incident and Service Request Process Definition?
- Do you distribute Incident and Service Request tickets?
- Do you have a Major Incident definition?
- Do you have a Problem Management Process Definition?
- Do you maintain Problem records?
- Do you store Known error descriptions in a Known Error DB?

Configuration Management

- Do you have a Configuration Management Process Definition?
- Do you specify continuous integration variable types and relationships?
- Do you maintain continuous integration entries (in CMDB)?
- Do you store continuous integration CMDB verification results?
- Do you establish continuous integration baselines?

Change Management

- Do you have a Change Management Process Definition?
- Do you maintain Change records?
- Do you store Post Implementation Review results?
- Do you have an Emergency Change definition?
- Do you have a Schedule of Changes?
- Do you have Change reversal plans?

Release and Deployment Management

- Do you have a Release and Deployment Management Process Definition?
- Do you have a Release Policy?
- Do you devise Release Plans (per release) and acceptance criteria?
- Post release evaluation results?

Continual Service Improvement

- Do you have a Continual Service Improvement Process Definition?
- Do you maintain a register of improvement suggestions?

Annex III - Course Organization Checklist

Planning stage

- Have you clearly defined the learning outcomes, intended audience and pre-requisites for the course?
- Have all the trainers been made aware of the learning outcomes, intended audience and pre-requisites for the course?
- Have you considered whether this course should be first-come-first served or with selection of participants? High pre-requisites can make selection more suitable.
- Does the course format and content match the intended audience?
- Have you secured all resources that are needed to adequately deliver the training?
- Do you have a written and approved budget for the event? Have you checked clashes with other BioExcel events?
- Will participants have an opportunity to present their work (e.g. poster, flashtalks)?
- Have you arranged ample social networking time (e.g. sufficient time for breaks (min 30 min), evening dinners, digital platform such as slack channel, or a living document)?

Event details and materials

- Are the learning outcomes, intended audience and pre-requisites clearly stated and available to potential applicants?
- Do you have a BioExcel events page that includes all of the following:
 - Event Overview
 - Learning outcomes
 - Intended audience, including pre-requisites
 - Course duration
 - Registration procedure and potential requirements (e.g. letter of support, motivation statement)
 - Registration fee and what it does and doesn't include (e.g. accommodation/food)
 - Draft programme (incl. lecture/hands-on/discussion)
 - Tools covered
 - Contributions expected by the participant (e.g. poster, participant flashtalks)
- Do the course format/learning activities/course materials match the intended audience and are the pre-requisites correct and clearly identified? Are your learning activities chosen to facilitate discussion and learning uptake?

Preparation

- Have you inspected the training facility site to make sure it is fit for purpose; if not in person images should be requested?

- Are all necessary learning resources (printed materials, digital materials, audio-visual equipment, computers, user accounts etc.) ready for use (ideally a week ahead)?
- Do you have a process for collecting event feedback from both trainees and trainers?

During the event

- Do you have a facilitator present during the entire event as a clear point of contact for participants?
- Have you allocated someone to summarise the previous days course content and give an overview of the coming day?

Evaluation and follow-up

- Do you have a post-course meeting planned with the organisers to discuss the feedback from the attendees and the trainers?
- Have you reported user needs information relevant to the consortium through T3.5 channels?
- Have you sent a follow up email to the participants with links to the material, facilitated a way for participants to keep in touch, and any relevant follow up messages?

Marketing

- Is the BioExcel logo clearly visible on all materials?

Generic

- Have you/the trainers attended a BioExcel's train-the-trainer course?